

The role of the TSN controller in E2E deterministic services provisioning

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ABSTRACT

The provisioning of deterministic services over E2E multi-technological infrastructures requires the proper configuration of the resources to match the required Key Performance Indicators (KPI), such as latency and jitter. From an architectural point of view, such configuration is carried out by an SDN-based TSN Controller that has the responsibility to control multiple technologies. In this paper, the main challenges of the TSN controller in such scenario are deeply discussed and its role and implementation in the TIMING architecture is also discussed.

Keywords: SDN Controller, Time Sensitive Networking, 6G Networks.

1. INTRODUCTION

The evolution towards future 6G infrastructure is marked, among others, with the advent of what is known as Time Sensitive Networking (TSN) [1] as an answer to time engineered business models and applications requiring of finely controlled temporal Key Performance Indicators (KPI), such as end-to-end (E2E) latency, jitter and resiliency. TSN refers both to the concept of time-bound use cases (UCs) as well as the infrastructures supporting them. In this regard, during the recent years, there have been significant efforts on developing data plane technologies in order to provide guaranteed transmission delays across network systems, specially in electronic switching network fabrics [2]. Several of the aforementioned UCs, such as, Industry 4.0 or augmented reality, will require the setting of traffic flows across a geographically distributed area, for instance, to interconnect the users with remote functions being executed in computational sites. Hence, it becomes necessary to extend the TSN capabilities to the full multi-segment/domain infrastructure. In this regard, optical networks arise as an ideal candidate to enable the interconnection between client TSN-able domains due to their deterministic nature by design [3]. Hence, TSN and optical segments should collaborate in the provisioning process to allocate suitable resources to support applications' requirements, namely, traffic queues at TSN segments and lightpaths (LPs) at optical ones.

Aside from the pure transmission of the data flows, one crucial aspect to enable TSN capabilities at a network infrastructure relates to the enforcement of the KPIs during the provisioning of traffic flows as well as the maintenance of said KPIs during the lifecycle of the established flows. Indeed, temporal KPI maintenance (e.g., latency, jitter) is a challenging task that requires a profound knowledge of the underlying data plane, its topology, employed technologies and exploitable capabilities, while also requiring the means to enforce configurations towards the desired goals in an automatic and efficient way. Thus, the presence of a control plane becomes of the essence [4].

The Software Defined Networking (SDN) paradigm has raised as one of the leading frameworks for the implementation of the control plane of TSN infrastructures [5]. It allows to have a centralized entity which then may interact with data plane technologies and configure them according to higher level directives. Nevertheless, the presence of multiple heterogeneous data planes, wired (e.g., ethernet, optical) and wireless (e.g., WiFi, 3GPP), each one with its own set of semantics and TSN-able capabilities, adds an extra layer of challenge on the definition and implementation of SDN solutions for TSN controllers. In this regard, in this paper we further elaborate the main challenges that an SDN-based TSN (SDN-TSN) controller needs to face and present the architecture of a developed solution within the context of the project TIMING, validating the operation of the controller by means of an experimental proof of concept (PoC). The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the reference scenario and the TIMING project; Section 3 elaborates on the challenges of an SDN-TSN controller, using as reference the proposed architecture for the control plane within TIMING; Section 4 describes the PoC of the proposed controller and depicts the experimental validations done; finally, Section 5 derives the main conclusions of the work.

2. REFERENCE SCENARIO

As introduced in the previous section, Industry 4.0 is one of the main UCs that pushes the need for supporting E2E time-bounded KPIs, either for the communication within factory floors (FFs), such as between in-site control functions and robotic arms or guided vehicles, or the intercommunication of multiple FFs for coordinating industrial processes in a large geographical area. The Spanish TIMING project [6] aims at the design of a solution that enables E2E reliable TSN services for Industry 4.0 supported by the operators' infrastructures that are currently relying on a best-effort (BE) traffic management basis. TIMING is analysing

the TSN support in the Ethernet and Wi-Fi segments so as to identify the enhancements to be made to support ultra-reliable, low latency communications (URLLC), with high reliability, high availability and low jitter for TSN services in coexistence with non-TSN (e.g., BE) ones. Scheduling solutions to support these enhancements are being devised. Moreover, solutions to automate the deployment of E2E TSN services with assured performance are designed, relying on a hierarchical control plane and a digital twin (DT) KPI estimation tool that includes accurate TSN traffic models.

Thus, the considered scenario involves the interconnection of multiple FF networks by means of a distribution metro network, for which optical technologies may be employed. Figure 1 depicts a schematic of the considered data plane and its main components, as well as the entities developed within TIMING for the control and management of the infrastructure to enable the provisioning of time-guaranteed communication services [7]. The FF network employ both advanced wireless (WiFi) nodes to enable high mobility end-points, such as automated guided vehicles (AGV), as well as wired nodes (Ethernet) for the backbone of the FF network and the interconnection towards the outside infrastructure. The wireless nodes are equipped with a network scheduler which determines the scheduling of the data flows into the time slots of the wireless communication so as to ensure that TSN traffic is served with the desired KPIs. Then, on top of the multiple network segments, lays the associated control entity. In this regard, in order to control the TSN-able segments, an instance of an SDN-TSN controller is employed, which engages at the same time with the wireless and wired infrastructure at the FFs. As for the metro network, it is configured by means of a dedicated metro controller instance. In order to coordinate the configuration of all segments and translate the requirements posed by external service petitions to exact connectivity requirements, an E2E Connectivity Manager (CM) acts as the overall system orchestrator, engaging in one hand with all network controllers, and in the other hand, with DT having detailed information of currently installed flows and their characteristics, for KPI assessment of prospecting network paths to be employed during the provisioning of the flows.

Figure 1. TIMING general architecture.

3. SDN CONTROLLER FOR TSN

Although the previous section has focused on the particular scenario of the TIMING project, in essence, it generally shows the main interactions and entities involved with an SDN – TSN controller in the configuration of data plane hardware for the establishment of time sensitive services. As such, in this section we use the specific case of the SDN – TSN Controller within TIMING as a case study for discussing the main responsibilities such an entity needs to assume and the related challenges that are involved. All in all, the SDN – TSN controller is the entity responsible for the configuration of the TSN-able hardware at the data plane, serving as intermediary between higher level entities (such as the presented CM) and the underlying infrastructure. In addition, it is also a crucial element to enable the provisioning decisions take at upper layers, since, having the detailed knowledge of the capabilities of the hardware elements at the controlled segments, it becomes the source of information for topology exposure and high-level capabilities of the multiple network nodes, which is essential in aligning client requests to flow characteristics. Nevertheless, although simple in their statement, both sets of operations require of several functionalities in order to be materialized, each one faced with their own challenges. To facilitate the discussion, let us depict in Figure 2 below a more detailed view of the SDN-TSN controller, highlighting both the functional components and the information/artefacts treated in each one of them.

First and foremost, all the control functionalities in a network infrastructure (e.g., request reception, exposure, configuration) are articulated thanks to the presence of rich data models [8], which allow for the efficient information exchange between entities, the understanding of the capabilities at all layers and the abstraction of unnecessary complexities. This is also certain in TSN infrastructures: it is necessary to know the capabilities of the underlying network nodes/devices so as to enforce the desired temporal KPIs (e.g., latency). Indeed, capability exposure, and its representation to upper layers, it is especially critical for the provisioning of time sensitive services. For example, and considering the transmission of packet data flows, several of the TSN hardware works in slotted/synchronized transmission so as to guarantee that packets are generated and switched

at precise times in order to fulfil the desired E2E latencies and jitters. Thus, the knowledge of the information related to the synchronization, prioritization and similar parameters for the traffic flows is something that every capabilities model in TSN infrastructures must consider and adapt. Such information then also needs to be carried to the representation of the connectivity services and associated flows, which enable the provisioning requests from upper layers (e.g., the CM following the TIMING example). These data models are handled by the Provisioning Manager (PM) in the presented diagram.

One very important aspect in this regard relates to the representation of the network topology, since it is a crucial piece of information for upper layers in order to decide which network paths and, as a consequence, which configurations should be enforced in order to fulfil the service KPIs. The topology needs to be nurtured by the multiple models (resources and capabilities), providing an abstract view of the infrastructure layout with the enough grain of detail to facilitate decision taking. In the context of this work, the IETF Deterministic Networking (DetNet) topology model has been adopted [9], enhancing it with custom extensions so as to account for the particular characteristics of the underlying data plane within the project. As has been said before, time sensitive services require of time-bounded KPIs, thus, the topology should also provide some degree of information about the achievable latency between network spans or across the nodes. In practice, this is a very difficult aspect, since it requires a deep understanding of the underlying hardware (i.e., type of transmission, port scheduling, etc.) as well as which is the concatenation of sub-systems across a particular network link, which sometime is not information that can be easily exposed, both for scalability and security reasons. Thus, alternative solutions need to be adopted. A common approach is to characterize the abstracted topology with macroscopic parameters, such as link length, achievable bit-rate or buffer size, which would then allow to derive some rough estimate about the KPIs. However, this then would require means for KPI assessment. In the context of the presented architecture, this is done by the DT, which implements various statistical models and machine learning (ML) procedures to provide a fine estimate of the KPIs that a flow to be established will experience. For this regard, a consistent inventory of the currently established flows, as well as the assigned resources is required, which is handled by the Inventory Manager in the depicted architecture.

Last, but not least, the frictionless coexistence of multiple TSN data planes is a requirement that the SDN-TSN controller needs to handle. As explained before, the proper coordination and alignment of configuration parameters at low level across multiple data planes is a must for time-bounded data transmissions. Hence, it is on the interest of the overall well-functioning of the infrastructure that the controller is able to configure multiple data planes, wireless and wired, from the same entity. In order to facilitate the coexistence of multiple data planes as well as configuration protocols, the concept of adapter has been defined. An adapter is a module that acts as a wrapper for the configuration of the underlying data planes. It offers an abstracted technology-agnostic view of the configuration endpoints of the data plane hardware to the provisioning service, or other modules within the SDN-TSN controller. On the lower part of each adapter, it implements the specific configuration protocol and operations that are dependent of the hardware that needs to be configured. Such structuring allows for a more flexible way of communicating with the remote hardware, facilitating the extensions of new operations or communication protocols, or the incorporation of new hardware to be controlled. For the specific example, the implementation of the SDN-TSN controller implements two adapters, one for the wired domain and another for the wireless one, implementing at their turn in the technology specific part of the adapter a REST and an SSH client, respectively, for communicating with a wired Central Network Controller (CNC) or modify remotely the configuration files multiple wireless access points (APs).

Figure 2. Functional block diagram of the SDN-TSN controller.

4. TIME SENSITIVE SERVICE PROVISIONING PROOF OF CONCEPT

To finalize, in this section we showcase the operation of the proposed SDN-TSN controller, enriched by means of the several functionalities explained during the previous section. For the sake of space, we will only focus on the outcome. To this end, we consider the presence of one WiFi AP (AP1) and one Ethernet switch (SW1) interconnected with each other, both of them implementing TSN-capable hardware. Then, a request to establish a TSN flow, with bounded time KPIs across them is received by the SDN-TSN controller, stating the desired path and TSN requirements. Fig. 3 depicts a sample of the SDN-TSN controller and AP system log, as well as the dashboard of the CNC, focusing on the result of the configuration. The SDN-TSN controller then translates the stated path to internal configurations, such as priority and VLAN tags for the flows, and communicates with the nodes through the corresponding adapter (Fig 3. a). As a result, the wired switch is activated with the desired configuration (Fig 3. b) and the new parameters for the up- and downlinks at the AP are configured (Fig 3. c). The final result is the establishment of a TSN-compliant flow following the stated path. This is achieved thanks to the multiple solutions adopted to overcome the posed challenges by heterogeneous TSN-able data planes in regards of control and configuration.

Figure 3. Flow provisioning PoC.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We reviewed the role of an SDN – TSN controller within the context of time sensitive services and network infrastructures. One crucial aspect that such entity needs to implement is the enforcement of configurations in compliance with strict temporal KPIs across multiple coordinated data plane technologies. We discussed how this can be achieved thanks to a system of rich data models and adapters, which allow a frictionless coexistence and configuration of both wireless and wired hardware.

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